

Effect of concentration and pH on zirconia nanostructure prepared by aqueous gelation method

Seena Kurakaran* and Abraham George

Department of Chemistry, Mar Ivanios College, University of Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram-695 015, Kerala, India

E-mail : seenakurakaran@gmail.com

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Abstract : Zirconia nano particles were synthesized by aqueous gelation method. As the concentration of sodium acetate was increased, the pH increased and the gelation time decreased. At low concentration of sodium acetate (0.01 M), tetragonal zirconia with small amounts of monoclinic phase was formed. But as the concentration of sodium acetate was raised, the amount of tetragonal phase decreased and the amount of monoclinic phase increased. At the same time, the average particle size also increased from 20 to 93 nm. The phases were identified using XRD and the particle size was calculated using the Scherrer formula. The TEM of one sample is also reported.

Keywords : Zirconia, aqueous gelation, tetragonal, monoclinic.

Introduction

Zirconia is an important material for high technique functional and structural applications. It shows a lot of interesting properties like superior thermal stability, heat-insulating performance, low heat conductivity and excellent mechanical property and has been used as high temperature coating and other devices^{1,2,17,18}. The tetragonal to monoclinic phase transformation is of technological importance as it contributes to the toughening of ceramics, and has attracted much attention over the past decades^{3,4,20,21}. Sulphated zirconia is a well-known solid acid catalyst^{5,6,15} and has shown potential applications at ambient temperature.

As such there has been a growing interest in the preparation of zirconia based ceramic powders with the required characteristics of size, purity, uniformity, crystallinity etc. For catalytic applications of zirconia appropriate textural properties such as high surface area, well-developed pore structure in micro- and mesoporous regions that they are resistant to sintering are of vital importance. Surface properties and catalytic activity are also affected by the crystal form of ZrO₂, therefore the phase composition of zirconia should be controlled while engineering catalysts for the desired applications. However, during preparation of ZrO₂ by the conventional precipi-

tation from aqueous solutions of the precursor zirconyl salt, usually a mixture of the monoclinic and tetragonal forms is produced.

Therefore the use of more adequate preparation procedures leading specifically to the desired form of zirconium oxide has to be applied^{7,8,19}. Particular emphasis has been placed upon co-precipitation, sol-gel, hydrothermal processing and polymerized complex processes. Difficulties with most of these techniques mainly involving cost and environmental issues preclude their commercial utilization. Therefore practical methods are still needed for the synthesis of high-quality zirconia powders with the required characteristics.

Aqueous gelation method has turned out to be a simple and excellent route for the preparation of zirconia nanostructures⁹. The aqueous gelation method has many advantages viz. a highly homogenous crystalline product can be obtained directly at a relatively lower reaction temperature, (<150 °C), favors a decrease in agglomeration between particles, narrow particle size distribution, phase homogeneity, uniform composition, high product purity and controlled particle morphology¹⁰. Moreover the reaction takes place at ordinary laboratory conditions with less expensive chemicals. There is a wide scope of using this method to produce other oxide materials with required properties for catalysis.

In the present work, we discuss the effect of sodium acetate concentration on the gelation time, particle size distribution and phase transformation of zirconia prepared by the reaction between zirconyloxchloride and sodium acetate by aqueous gelation¹¹ technique.

Results and discussion

Preparation :

The aqueous gelation method using sodium acetate can be considered as a highly versatile method. Here five samples of zirconium dioxide were prepared using different concentrations of sodium acetate. The pH of the solutions were found to be 1.22, 3.83, 4.54, 4.92 and 5.28 for 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05 M concentrations of sodium acetate respectively. This pH¹⁶ was conducive for the formation of the gel. The acetate ions function as a good ligand coordinating to Zr controlling its hydrolysis, leading to the formation of $ZrO_{2-x}(OH)_{2x}\cdot yH_2O$ ¹².

X-Ray diffraction analysis :

XRD profile of the five ZrO_2 nanostructures synthesized at 600 °C for five different concentrations of sodium acetate is given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction of ZrO_2 prepared to various concentration.

The diffraction peaks in the spectrum for 0.01 M CH_3COONa is composed of *t*- ZrO_2 with minor quantities of *m*- ZrO_2 . Almost all the diffraction peaks with similar relative intensity as suggested in the JCPDS data are observed in the experimental XRD pattern and are significantly sharp, hence confirming the high crystallinity of the synthesized ZrO_2 sample. As the concentration of sodium acetate is increased, the pH of the reaction mixture increased. The XRD pattern shows that, the amount of *t*- ZrO_2 decreased and *m*- ZrO_2 phase becomes promi-

nent. The percentage of the two phases at each concentration is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Effect of concentration on pH, particle size, gelation time and relative amounts of phases of zirconia nanostructure prepared from 0.01 M zirconyloxchloride

Concentration of sodium acetate (M)	pH	Gelation time (h)	Particle size (nm)	Percentage of tetragonal phase	Percentage of monoclinic phase
0.01	1.22	4	20	80.24	19.76
0.02	3.83	3	42	73.68	26.32
0.03	4.54	1	56	37.27	62.73
0.04	4.92	>1	72	31.80	68.20
0.05	5.28	>1	93	21.64	78.36

Particle size :

Size of ZrO_2 nano structure prepared by aqueous gelation was calculated from XRD data using the Scherrer equation. With the increasing concentration of CH_3COONa , the particle size of ZrO_2 was found to increase. The size of the particles for the different concentrations was found to be 20, 42, 56, 72 and 93 nm respectively. The particle size also influences the phase transformation. Particles smaller than a critical size do not go through the reverse transformation and remain in a metastable tetragonal form at room temperature. Wang *et al.* did a complete review on transformation temperatures (*m-t* and *t-m*) for zirconia (ZrO_2).

The transition path from the monoclinic to the tetragonal phase or whether the transition is proper are not known¹³. The particle size at each concentration is given in Table 1.

Gelation time :

The reaction mixture was observed for the formation of gel. With the increasing concentration of sodium acetate, gelation took place rapidly. For higher concentrations, turbidity seems to appear instantly and the gel is formed within one hour. For lower concentrations, turbidity appears after one hour and gelation starts to appear after three hours. Gel is not formed with a very low concentration of sodium acetate. The variation in gelation time for each concentration of sodium acetate is given in Table 1.

Phase transformation :

The powder consists of tetragonal phase and minor

monoclinic phase at lower concentration of sodium acetate. The amount of monoclinic ZrO_2 was enhanced with increase in concentration of sodium acetate. This result can be explained on the basis of the surface energy difference relative to the particle size. A particle with tetragonal structure has lower surface energy than that of monoclinic structure when the size is very small. As a result, the smaller particle is preferentially stabilized with the tetragonal structure, and a larger one with the monoclinic structure. Further, the structural information of the ZrO_2 nanostructure was studied by TEM. Fig. 2 shows the TEM image of ZrO_2 of 0.01 M, showing tiny cylindrical particles with diameters below 25 nm and particle with regular cylindrical shaped nanostructures.

Fig. 2. TEM image of ZrO_2 nanomaterial synthesized by aqueous gelation method.

These results are in accordance with thermodynamic attribution of the enhanced stabilization of the *t*- ZrO_2 polymorphs to the particle size effect.

As it was already mentioned, an opposite decrease of the surface free energy on passing from monoclinic to tetragonal structure for crystallites with diameters smaller than the critical size of ~ 30 nm provides the driving force for stabilization of the latter form. Results of Garvie showed that below 30 nm the meta stable- ZrO_2 is stable in nano crystal ZrO_2 and above this value *m*- ZrO_2 will be stable^{14,22,23}.

Experimental

Synthesis of ZrO_2 nano materials at varying concentrations of sodium acetate :

ZrO_2 nanostructures were synthesized by a simple aqueous gelation technique. Zirconyloxychloride octahydrate and sodium acetate were used as the starting materials for the synthesis. All the chemicals were of analytical grade and used without further purification. $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ (0.01 M) was taken in five autoclavable bottles and were stirred vigorously using a magnetic stirrer. Varying concentrations (0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05 M) of CH_3COONa were added drop wise to the zirconyloxychloride respectively with constant stirring. The clear homogeneous mixture¹¹ obtained was then maintained at 110 °C. The time taken for the formation of gel for different concentrations was observed. The gel was centrifuged using a high speed centrifuge and washed several times with distilled water and dried in air. The white powders so obtained were calcined in an alumina crucible in a muffle furnace at 600 °C for 4 h. Fine white powder of zirconia thus obtained was subjected to instrumental analysis.

Structural characterization :

The X-ray diffractogram (XRD) of all the samples were recorded on a Siemens D-5000 X-ray diffractometer with a $Cu K\alpha$ -radiation (wavelength 1.54 Å). The observed data was compared with JCPDS standards. The relative amount of tetragonal and monoclinic phases and the particle size were calculated from the X-ray diffractogram. The Scherrer equation was used to calculate the particle size. The TEM of one sample was recorded on a JEOL 3010 machine operating at an accelerating voltage of 300 kV. For TEM analysis, the ZrO_2 was ultrasonically dispersed in ethanol and then spread on carbon-coated copper grids and dried under vacuum.

Conclusion

ZrO_2 nano particles were synthesized using varying concentrations of sodium acetate by aqueous gelation method with zirconium oxychloride as the starting material. With increase in concentration of sodium acetate, the pH increased and gelation time decreased. When gel formation became faster, the particle size increased and more of monoclinic phase was formed. Tetragonal zirconium oxide transformed to monoclinic zirconium oxide with prolonged crystallization time accompanied with the increase of particle size.

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